

THE ROLE OF INTEGRATED EDUCATION IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of integrated education in teaching English in the educational system.

Key words: foreign languages, integration, methodology, educational system, pedagogue.

Learning English is becoming one of the priorities of the modern education system. Cultural and social doors open to speakers of this language are all economic doors open, as the use of English creates more study and work opportunities. The latter is highly valued in terms of the competitiveness of the labor market of each country. In the era of rapid scientific development, interdisciplinary integration is of crucial importance in the establishment of continuous education. The term integration is derived from the Latin word *integratio*, which means joining, uniting. Integrating information means combining and presenting material from various sources based on a specific purpose. Integrated education and interdisciplinary communication are two different concepts that complement each other.

Interdisciplinary communication refers to communication established between educational subjects in order to allow the student to understand this or that problem as deeply as possible in the process of mastering certain knowledge and effectively put the acquired knowledge into practice. And integration is a coherent, comprehensive, and comprehensive approach to interdisciplinary communication, that is, the leading ideas and phenomena specific to the studied problem, relying on the knowledge obtained in general sciences, academic subjects, their departments and topics. means opening. We can observe that integrated education has its place in teaching English.

The teacher's role in getting the child interested in thinking and in various fields is also justified in this approach. In addition, interdisciplinary communication will increase significantly. In different parts of the educational system, children in preschool education, students of primary education (ages 7-11) and students of higher classes are learning a foreign language in the educational process. An integrated approach can be used along with game technology in primary education. For students of the upper class, it is also a factor in broadening the

thinking and worldview. The above will stimulate the country's growth and technological development. Managing computer networks such as the Internet is essential in a variety of production and entertainment systems. In this way, there is a need to introduce these technologies into pedagogical practice as part of a new teaching strategy. Thus, the use of technologies in the process of language teaching leads to greater efficiency.

An integrated system of interdisciplinary lessons should make up a large part of the year-long training in a certain academic subject. Acquired knowledge can be defined as follows: For example, describing various events of parts given in art books, familiarizing with geographical location, biological structure of creatures in it, familiarizing with plants, understanding emotions, thinking, feeling, sadness of a developing person. It affects the development of aspects such as being a friend.

In order to learn the solution of a problem based on interdisciplinary communication, the teacher must first clearly define the goal, review the studied material, choose appropriate methods for its effective learning, determine the form and necessary materials for organizing the lesson process, and it is required to determine in advance the results to be obtained.

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